

Automation

Green Photonics

Telecoms and Datacoms

Create your business in Photonics!

Biophotonics
Security

Photonics in Sweden

Photonics in Sweden has experienced a profound transformation since the years 2000. From a strong focus on telecom application driven by Ericsson and Telia Sonera, it has been diversifying to basically all main applications of photonics.

While keeping an impressive strength in the telecoms, Swedish photonics has a particularly large potential of growth in automation, green photonics and biophotonics.

Mature photonics technologies

Mature and edge photonics technologies in Sweden are e.g.: IR detection systems based on cameras from FLIR Systems and detectors from IR Nova IR sensors are also used in gas sensing devices from Sensair are also world leading in their field. In the telecom area there are many companies active from large suppliers and users like Ericsson and Telia to top notch component suppliers like Transmode (recently integrated in Infinera), Finisar and TE Connectivity. Proximion produces advanced fiber Bragg gratings and ACREO provides special optical fibers. Other components suppliers are in the laser field with diode-pumped solid-state lasers from Cobolt and the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH). Laser technology for medical diagnostics and treatment are developed at the Lund Laser Center and in spin-off companies like Spectracure. Surface-Plasmon Resonance detectors are provided from GE Healthcare Biosciences. Several research groups are working on thin-film photovoltaic as well as companies like Solibro and Midsummer. Many companies provide intelligent vision systems including SAAB Systems and eye tracking and eye control systems from Tobii. X-ray detector systems from several companies and high brilliance sources from Excillum.

PHOTONICS APPLICATIONS RELEVANT FOR THE FUTURE

Biophotonics

Sweden is the country of very important innovations in the life sciences, e.g. the pacemaker just to name one, and has a very strong academic research in medicine, veterinary, pharmaceuticals and agriculture. In that context, the about 40 and usually small Swedish companies active in biophotonics seem to have a large growth potential.

There is an increasing need for diagnostics and monitoring tools and the emergence of photonic innovations for the life science will be huge if an efficient dialogue is ensured between end-users, practitioners, technology providers and integrators. Obviously, the collaboration should also be, and is being, increased with other key technologies.

Automation

Automation of the industry is a key to maintain manufacturing or reindustrialize Western countries. It requires the use of advanced technology. For this machine vision and optical instruments to analyze and monitor industrial processes are increasingly used.

Swedish companies within automation have a turnover of about 5 billion Euros and our country has a long tradition of large companies and is very well positioned to lead “Photonics for factory automation”.

Telecoms and Datacoms

The share of the telecoms in the Swedish photonics industry has decreased substantially since the early years 2000. Some very advanced companies and products have nevertheless been able to get good positions on the market, such as Transmode, Finisar Sweden, TE Connectivity and Proximion.

Ericsson has recently increased their interest in photonic technologies beyond fiber communication. It is likely that the building of 5G systems will require advanced integrated photonic integrated circuits and the involvement of Swedish companies.

Green Photonics

Sweden is one of the world's leading nations innovating, implementing and exporting Green Technologies, commonly known as Greentech or Cleantech. On the other hand, the use of photonics for Cleantech or green photonics is a field which is still in its infancy in Sweden.

Several Swedish companies develop new types of solar cells, e.g. CIGS thin-films or Graetzel type cells. There are excellent conditions in Sweden to make internet less energy hungry with photonic techniques. An interesting technology is the cleaning of water for developing countries and in the medical sector with light, either through UV LED or with sunlight as the company Solvatten is doing.

Security

Sweden is an important player in the development of security materials, both military and civil. In the defense sector, Saab is a big player stimulating surrounding companies. In the civilian sector, the company AHAB (now Hexagon) monitoring hydrographic topography should be mentioned.

Sweden has a particularly strong position in the field of thermal imaging with actors such as FLIR, IR Nova and Acreo.

Support for entrepreneurship in Photonics in Sweden

Essentially all universities have hubs and strategies to support entrepreneurship and start-up companies. These are not dedicated particularly to Photonics companies, Ideon in Lund and Lund "Nyföretagscentrum" as well as KTH Innovation, Stockholm Innovation and Growth (STING) have a very strong track record and they have helped tenth of photonics companies.

Spirit Ventures (Quan Funds LLC) is a venture capitalist who is specialized on financing companies which are active (or which are start-ups) in the KET (Key Enabling Technology) areas.

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Photonics4All is a European Horizon 2020 Outreach project, funded by the European Commission to promote photonics and light based technologies to young people, entrepreneurs and the general public across the EU. Photonics4all's unique selling point is that it will both develop a set of new promotional tools and apply them during a wide variety of outreach activities with different audiences.

*Discover our unique approach and check out our tools and events :
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Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light